

THE USAGE OF HOMOGENEOUS SUBJECTS IN ENGLISH: PREDICATIVE AND NON-PREDICATIVE CONNECTIONS

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It is known that, coming one or more than two subjects in a sentence are called homogeneous subjects. Homogeneous subjects may follow predicate and attribute themselves. But homogeneous subjects usually determined with relative of predicates.

A syntactic unity of a simple sentence structure may be clarified in syntactic. We can analysis the homogeneous subjects which came in spite of kernel predicate with separating.

Syntactic and morphology have mutual relation; they can fulfill each other in a sentence. Morphological unity, word forms take shape in word combination and sentence. There is a mutual relation between parts of sentence and word classes. Syntactic communications, which can be met in diverse language, are divided into two types:

Predicative and non-predicative connection.

The predicative connection is the components base of sentence structure (base of grammar) is a connection of and syntactic communication. A sentence is made up with them.

Homogeneous subjects in English sentence Mr. Radish and Mrs. Lancaster remarked are suitable for person and number and make a syntactic communication. Non predicative connection does not have such peculiarities. Such kinds of words make a syntactic communication in diverse ways and forms. Equal connection and fellow connection, which called types of syntactic communication are types of non-predicative communication.

If we discuss the first type, we will grasp the concerned sides of our theme. Because, in this type equal connective words make a grammatic connection equally.

On the whole, it is possible to talk about syntactic connection of English language for a long time.

His brother and also his sister are asleep.

The homogeneous subjects are equally connected, and show coordinative connection.

In English language the elements which came as a subject are not only noun, pronoun, number but also they will be a subject with affixes. If a preposition belongs to predicate, at that time it means objectiveness.

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